

MAELSTROM

MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D9.1

Plan for Communication and Dissemination

30/06/2021

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Executive Summary

The present document refers to the Plan for Communication and Dissemination of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM - MARinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management. It is intended to be used both as a guiding document by the consortium's members and as an informative report to the EU, detailing efforts carried in the first six months of the project cycle and efforts planned for the year ahead. The document is deliverable 9.1 of Work Package 9 – and it is structured in two main chapters:

- **Dissemination Strategy:** it refers to ongoing and future efforts to promote and facilitate the use of MAELSTROM's research results among potential users and peers within research, industry, commercial and policy-making fields.
- **Communication Strategy:** it refers to ongoing and future efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting the project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, engaging in a two-way exchange.

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1. Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

2. MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

	National Research Council	CNR	Project Coordinator Fantina MADRICARDO fontina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it
Deltares	Deltares	Deltares	Frans BUSCHMAN Frans.Buschman@deltares.nl
	University of Malta	UOM	Luciano MULE' STAGNO luciano.mule-stagno@um.edu.mt
	The International Sustainable Development Initiatives	ISDI	Manuel SCARPA m.scarpa@isdigroup.com
	Gees Recycling Srl	GEES	Giorgio BETTETO geesretracking@gmail.com
	Venice Lagoon Plastic Free	VLPF	Davide POLETTA d.poletta@plasticfreevenice.org
	CIMA Research Foundation	CIMA	Isabel GOMES isabel.gomes@cimafoundation.org
	TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	Damien SALLÉ damien.salle@tecnalia.com
	ALPHA Consult	ALPHA UK	Emiliano SPALTRO es@alphacons.eu
	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research	CIIMAR	Isabel SOUSA-PINTO ispinto@ciimar.up.pt
	Servizi Tecnici	ST	Nicola FERRARI n.ferrari@stvenezia.com
	The Great Bubble Barrier	TGBB	Philip EHRHORN philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.goutteforde@lirmm.fr

3. Aims of the Deliverable

The present document refers to the dissemination and communication plan (DCP) of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM - MARinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management. It is intended to be used both as a guiding document by the consortium's members and as an informative report to the EU, detailing efforts carried in the first six months of the project cycle and efforts planned for the year ahead. The document is deliverable 9.1 of Work Package 9 – and it is structured in two main chapters:

- **Dissemination Strategy:** it refers to ongoing and future efforts to promote and facilitate the use of MAELSTROM's research results among potential users and peers within research, industry, commercial and policy-making fields.
- **Communication Strategy:** it refers to ongoing and future efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting the project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, engaging in a two-way exchange.

The present DCP aims to provide a concise and clear guidance, defining actions, messages, players, and tools. Although structured in two separate chapters, the dissemination and communication efforts will converge in achieving common goals, namely:

- Increase the **success and reputation** of MAELSTROM project, highlighting the consortium's identity, efforts, skills, innovations, and initiatives.
- Draw the **attention of multiple stakeholders** and audiences regarding marine litter impacts on ecosystems and on the existing solutions to mitigate them.
- Demonstrate the way **MAELSTROM's outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives**, by introducing novel technologies and improving lives through environmental regeneration, the creation of new market's segments and associated jobs within a circular economy (from litter to regenerated raw materials).
- Create **market demand** for marine litter removal technologies and recycled products by fostering **awareness** on marine litter impacts, promote innovative solutions for litter removal and highlight the advantages of recycled products for the industrial supply chain.

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- Develop and deliver **economic feasibility** studies regarding the adoption, functioning and maintenance of MAELSTROM's removal technologies
- Make better use of the results, by assuring they are taken up by **decision-makers in policymaking**, as well as by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up. In MAELSTROM's case, it refers to the Joint Strategy that will be designed among key stakeholders to increase the communication and dissemination efforts of ongoing marine litter-related activities within the European space and beyond. The overarching goal is to contribute to the set-up of more efficient policies and legislation regarding marine litter identification, production, removal, and recycling within the European space.
- Demonstrate how the **European collaboration** has produced scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness and to solve a societal challenge as marine litter and its impacts on living ecosystems.

To achieve such goals dissemination and communication efforts will:

- **Transfer** MAELSTROM's solutions to a wide range of stakeholders and audiences
- **Mobilize** stakeholders and civil society on marine litter impacts, solutions, and behaviours
- **Create** capacity building regarding the use and maintenance of MAELSTROM's products
- **Shift** consumer's behaviour on plastic consumptions
- **Promote** circular economy as an effective and cost-beneficial paradigm

W.P.9 AIMS

Communication & Dissemination

Figure 1: MAELSTROM's Communication and Dissemination Goals

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4. Specific Communication and Dissemination purposes

MAELSTROM – MARinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management is a European Union-funded project under the call H2020-FNR-2021-1, ID: 101000832. The project is designed to develop and test sustainable technological solutions for the removal, treatment, and recycling of marine debris, leveraging on the integration of complementary technologies and following a circular economy approach which includes the marketization of regenerated and recycled materials.

MAELSTROM proposes to:

- Set out a reliable multidisciplinary and **scientific approach** for assessing marine debris distribution and its impacts on living organisms, in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas.
- Design and manufacture scalable, replicable, and automated **technologies**, co-powered by renewable energy and second-generation fuels, aimed at identifying, removing, and sorting marine debris.
- Evaluate over time the **effectiveness** of marine debris removal devices alongside their **impacts** for coastal ecosystems.
- Integrate different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected litter into valuable **raw materials for future marketisation**.
- Assess the **economic and societal impacts** of the solutions developed within the project, providing comprehensive life-cycle assessments of both technologies and derived products.
- Enhance **social awareness** about the marine debris issue and engage citizens and stakeholders in responsible behaviours, from consumerism to recycling.
- Interplay with similar projects to speed and **maximize innovation** uptake for marine debris removal within and outside the EU.

MAELSTROM is formally supported by a set of key partners committed to sustain its core actions and its follow up activities. The consortium is composed of 14 partners coming from 8 European countries, made of excellence research centers in the fields of marine life, biology, sustainable energy, artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. Other partners include private multinational /national recycling companies with certified industrial plants, a market consultancy company, a micro-enterprise, and a marine-litter/plastics orientated NGO. Pilot actions will take place in Italy and in Portugal.

MAELSTROM's key phases can be described as follows:

- **Localize & Characterize** – supported by advanced modelling techniques, marine debris trajectories and accumulation hotspots will be identified in the pilot areas of Venice (IT) and the nearby area of Porto (PT). An environmental assessment will be done to measure the impact of the accumulated debris in those hotspots for the surrounding ecosystem.
- **Collect** - MAELSTROM's removal technologies will be installed and tested in two pilot locations: the Bubble Barrier will be installed in the nearby area of Porto while the Underwater Cable Robot will be installed in Venice. A second environmental assessment will be made to assess the impacts of the technological devices and of the removal operation for the surrounding ecosystem, aiming at mitigating any possible trade-offs.
- **Sort & Transform** - removed debris will be sorted according to its typology. Plastic objects will be traced and will go through advanced recycling processes which will originate regenerated materials – such as chemical precursors, polymers and second generations fuels - useful for the industrial supply chain. Alongside the transformation processes, a prototype based on low-temperature pyrolysis capable of producing second-generation fuel from plastics, already developed on Margnet, a previous EU project (<https://www.margnet.eu/it/home/>) will be used in order to provide fuel to power MAELSTROM's removal technologies, creating a self-feeding cycle.
- **Marketize** - dedicated exploitation and scoping activities will be designed to facilitate the marketization of regenerated materials to enter the market chain.

Figure 2: Illustrated scheme on MAELSTROM's key phases

4.1. Target Audiences and Key Stakeholders

MAELSTROM's Consortium has identified ten main groups of stakeholders, likely to be interested on project outputs and outcomes.

Scientific

- Research/Academia and related communities interested in catalyzing scientific research and cooperation towards knowledge and technological development for marine litter identification, removal, and recycling, building upon on MAELSTROM's scientific and technological approaches and results.

Innovation/Technological

- Technological actors interested to industrialize MAELSTROM'S demonstrators by scaling up removal technologies and by replicating/developing related technologies for marine litter removal, sorting, tracking and recycling/regeneration.

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- Startups interested in developing systems to remove plastics from the environment.

Industrial

- Industry organizations (marine litter processors) interested in processing collected marine litter and engaged in transforming it into recycled materials to feed supply chains.
- Industry organizations (recycled materials consumers) interested in using regenerated and recycled materials in their supply chains for lower carbon impacts.

Market

- Market investors interested in scaling and commercializing MAELSTROM's technologies and products.
- Waste management & recycling companies interested in using MAELSTROM's technologies for increased and improved waste management capacities and recycling opportunities at local level.

Policy & Donors

- EU and EU Working Groups active on the fields of Plastics and Circular Economy, interested in up taking consortium's expertise and outcomes.
- Donors (UN, Private Foundations, National funds...) interested in investing in the development of science-based technological solutions to tackle marine litter, and to foster improved circular economy approaches and policies towards sustainable development.
- Policy makers/Authorities interested in benefiting from MAELSTROM's technologies, products and awareness-raising for their sphere of action.

Civil Society and Media

- Civil society organizations, NGO's and single citizens interested in being an active part of the marine litter global challenge, through responsible behaviours, advocacy, and collective actions at local level, such as beach clean-ups, awareness events and related initiatives (glocal concept – think globally, act locally).
- Media actors interested in creating citizen awareness and knowledge regarding marine litter impacts and MAELSTROM's proposed solutions; interested in advocating for marine litter solutions, ranging from single

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behaviours to local, national, regional, and international global policies for marine litter production, removal, and exploitation.

5. Dissemination Strategy

5.1. Objectives and expected impacts of the dissemination activities

MAELSTROM's dissemination strategy refers to ongoing and future efforts to promote and facilitate the use of project's research results among potential users and peers within the fields of research, industry, commercial and policy. Dissemination activities will be focused on achieving a wide outreach of projects' activities in all its components, from research, to experimentation, outcomes, and impacts. Dissemination activities are to be considered an all-partners task as this is the only modality to guarantee a constant and successful outreach. Although main dissemination efforts are expected to take place from the second year on, following the implementation and testing phases of MAELSTROM's technologies in the pilot areas of Venice and Porto, main messages of the dissemination activities will focus on promoting the following aspects:

- Effectiveness and further opportunities of multidisciplinary **scientific approaches** – from modeling to environmental assessment - for the identification of marine debris distribution and its impacts on coastal ecosystems.
- Effectiveness and further opportunities of multidisciplinary scientific approaches to assess the **impacts** of removal technologies for coastal ecosystems.
- Latest design and advancements regarding automated low-carbon **technologies** for marine debris identification and removal, making use of artificial intelligence and robotics.
- Effectiveness of **MAELSTROM's technological solutions** for the removal of marine debris.
- Outcomes of technologies' integration for tracking, sorting, and recycling marine debris and converting it into **recycled materials for marketization**.

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- Benefits and effectiveness of second-generation products for the industrial supply chains.
- Possible gaps and strategic activities to be further developed by the scientific/technological community regarding the marine litter cycle.
- Economic and societal impacts of the solutions developed within the project through comprehensive life-cycle assessments of both technologies and derived products.
- Networking and interplay with alike projects, initiatives, and stakeholders to accelerate solutions towards the marine debris global challenge.
- Wide and cross-cutting stakeholder and society at large engagement to tackle marine litter.

Moreover, MAELSTROM's dissemination activities intend to contribute to the CNR-ISMAR Third Mission of transferring scientific research to society.

5.2. MAELSTROM's Consortium Dissemination Players

While CIMA is the Coordinator Partner regarding the dissemination and communication activities, all partners are expected to contribute to the dissemination and communication efforts. Considering the high scientifically and technological expertise required within the project, each partner will make efforts to disseminate project's outcomes within its own sphere of influence. Activities will be coordinated with CIMA, which will support and assure good visibility of each partner's efforts.

Dissemination Players, Aims, Tools and Channels		
WHO	AIMS	TOOLS & CHANNELS
<p><u>SCIENTIFIC PLAYERS</u></p> <p>From the consortium CNR-ISMAR, Deltares, CNRS, TECNALIA with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maximize result's impacts among the international scientific community. ▪ Disseminate scientific findings regarding project's aims. ▪ Contribute to the advancement of the state of the art. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thematic scientific conferences and events (ML, Robotics...). ▪ Peer reviewed scientific publications. ▪ Institutional website and channels. ▪ EU H2020/CORDIS magazines. ▪ Marine litter-related networks. ▪ MAELSTROM Web Forum.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make scientific results a common good by sharing data and knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos.
<p><u>TECHNOLOGICAL PLAYERS</u></p> <p>From the consortium EU, TECNALIA, CNRS, TGBB, UOM, I.S.D.I, ST, GEES with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminate technological advancements regarding marine debris removal practical solutions. Highlight the role of AI and robotics on answering societal challenges as the marine litter issue. Maximize result's impacts. Show the benefits of public-private partnerships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thematic scientific conferences and events (ML, Robotics...). Demonstrative events. Articles on technological, AI, Robotics magazines. EU H2020/CORDIS magazines. Marine litter-related networks. MAELSTROM Web Forum. MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos Institutional website and channels.
<p><u>INDUSTRIAL PLAYERS</u></p> <p>From the consortium EU, GEES, MAKEEN with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminate the benefits of recycled and regenerated marine debris products for the industrial supply chain within a virtuous circular economy paradigm. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trade associations. Supply chain networks. Demonstrative events. Articles on industrial thematic magazines. EU H2020/CORDIS magazines Institutional website and channels. Marine litter-related networks. MAELSTROM Web Forum. MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos.
<p><u>MARKET PLAYERS</u></p> <p>From the consortium EU, ALPHA UK, TECNALIA with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminate the socio-economic benefits of blue and circular economy solutions as promoted by MAELSTROM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine litter derived products networks. Institutional website and channels. Articles in sector specific/economic magazines.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To create market demand for marine litter technologies with focus on MAELSTROM's solutions among waste/recycling management companies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MAELSTROM Web Forum. MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos.
<p><u>POLICY PLAYERS & DONORS</u></p> <p>Consortium as result of project's outcomes and communication efforts with support from EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share knowledge, skills and data on ML impacts and solutions. Foster science-based policy making regarding marine litter. Help to tackle the ML issue. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-police interface conferences at local, national, and regional levels. Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions (WP7). Plastics/ML working groups. EU H2020/CORDIS magazines. MAELSTROM Web Forum. MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos. Contribution to EU White/Green papers. Contribution to the Plastics/Marine Litter Policy Strategy application.
<p><u>CIVIL SOCIETY PLAYERS</u></p> <p>From the consortium EU, CIMA, VLPF, CNR-ISMAR with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate the proportions of the ML challenge, its impacts for living ecosystems and human health and up to date available technological solutions for mitigation. Promote a circular economy paradigm by showing how marine debris can become a new resource. Engage citizens in responsible consumption in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civil society dedicated events such a MAELSTROM's clean ups, info days and informative conferences. Project communication and outreach activities through website, social media, and informative products. Engagement with local schools and associations regarding the ML issue. MAELSTROM website, social media, newsletters and videos.

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	<p>general with a focus on plastics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Show the success of the EU collaboration. 	
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Table 1: Dissemination Players, Aims, Tools and Channels

5.3. Dissemination tools and channels

To successfully convey the dissemination efforts to the respective target audiences and reach the highest impact possible, the project consortium will refer to a tri-level strategy involving:

- Online dissemination, interaction, and engagement
- Non-electronic tools and channels
- Physical interactive tools and channels

5.3.1. Online dissemination, interaction and engagement

Online tools have the aim to give MAELSTROM a vast exposure on the web, while providing the consortium with an additional channel to share project's general information and materials and exchange feedback with interested stakeholders. Main online dissemination products for MAELSTROM include:

- **Project website** | www.maelstrom-h2020.eu
MAELSTROM's website has a double function: on one hand it intends to guarantee an easy access and a wide as possible exposure of the project towards all sorts of audiences; from another, it works as a repository for communication products designed to support project's outreach and

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dissemination efforts. Communication products are easily available and downloadable to any user wishing to promote the project under the Media section. The website is divided in five sections and regularly updated, giving users the possibility of following events, subscribing to the project newsletter, and registering to participate at the Interactive Forum. An interactive section on marine litter-related projects taking place in the European space is also being developed. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) parameters have been applied to guarantee straightforward access and visibility to project's website.

Action Plan:

1. Partner(s) to inform CIMA (Communication Coordinator) regarding relevant activities and events.
2. CIMA to interview/interact with partner(s) and decide on the best communication/dissemination output (ex. interview, news, post, press release...), in coordination with the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR).
3. CIMA to proceed with the publication on the selected channel.
4. All other partners to support and contribute to the outreach efforts.

▪ Project Newsletters

Biannual newsletters, starting in June 2021, will be delivered to partners, stakeholders, and registered users, containing key information on project's development and milestones, alongside events, activities and other relevant information regarding the project and different marine-litter-related themes.

Action Plan:

1. CIMA to collect relevant information regarding project's activities on the previous six months alongside future relevant events - directly and indirectly - related to the project.
2. CIMA to produce a first newsletter draft and to share it with Project Coordinator and Partners.
3. CIMA to collect suggestions and convey into a final version.
4. CIMA to publish and send newsletter through MailChimp to all partners, stakeholders, and registered users.

- **Interactive Forum & Webinars** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/forums/forum/maelstrom-forum/>

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MAELSTROM's website hosts an online Interactive Forum to be managed by project partner CIIMAR (Portugal). The platform focuses on addressing key topics regarding marine litter related research, initiatives and policies happening in the European space, representing an important tool to gather inputs from multiple stakeholders, through interactive discussions and thematic webinars. CIIMAR (PT) and MAELSTROM's consortium partners will mediate webinars regarding key topics such as, but not exclusively:

- Marine litter impacts on environmental and human health and the role of civil society to tackle the marine litter challenge.
- Strategies and innovative modelling to track ML and identify hotspots.
- Innovative technologies and solutions to collect and remove ML from the coastal ecosystems.
- Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Sort and Recycling ML.
- Exploitation of regenerated products: best practices.

Action Plan:

1. CIMA to set the IT infrastructure to host the Forum
2. CIMA to train CIIMAR on Forum IT access and maintenance
3. CIIMAR to organize discussions/webinars with guests on key topics and to produce minutes to be shared among the community

The results from the Forum discussions will be used to create a Joint Strategy for Dissemination and Networking Activities regarding ML efforts in the European space, which will be delivered to the European Union, acknowledging all the contributions received.

▪ Research-targeted social media channels

Scientific publications achieved as a result of the project's efforts will be given wide outreach through its dissemination on the project website and specific social media channels such as Twitter, LinkedIn and Research Gate (leveraging on researchers own account's).

Action Plan:

1. Project Coordinator or Consortium member to send publication notification to CIMA (info@maelstrom-h2020.eu).

2. CIMA to select key scientific messages to be published and after author's approval, to publish on relevant social media/website with a direct link to the journal.
3. Partners to contribute to the outreach efforts by re-publishing on their own professional and/or institutional accounts.

5.3.2. Non-electronic dissemination

- **Scientific publications**

Over the project duration, project partners commit to release scientific publications on marine litter/environmental impacts/removal and recycling related issues. Possible scientific journals and conferences interested in publishing MAELSTROM's outcomes are listed below.

Relevant Publications for MAELSTROM's Consortium			
TITLE	WEBSITE	PUBLISHER	IMPACT FACTOR
Frontiers in Marine Science	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/marine-science	Frontiers Media S.A.	3.661
Environmental Science: Water Research and Technology	https://www.rsc.org/journals-books-databases/about-journals/environmental-science-water-research-technology/	Royal Society of Chemistry	3.449
Monitoring of Mediterranean Coastal Areas	https://media.fupress.com/files/pdf/24/4402/15016	Firenze University Press	Catalogue
Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology	https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/best20	Taylor and Francis Ltd.	8.3
Resources, Conservation and Recycling	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/resources-conservation-and-recycling	Elsevier Ltd.	8.086
GCB Bioenergy	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/17571707	Wiley-VCH Verlag	5.316
IEEE Transactions on Robotics	https://www.ieeeras.org/publications/t-ro	IEEE	6.123

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IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=3516	IEEE	5.673
Mechanism and Machine Theory	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/mechanism-and-machine-theory	Elsevier	3.312
Sensors	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors	MDPI	3.275
Biomass and Bioenergy	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/biomass-and-bioenergy	Elsevier	3.551
Energy Strategy Reviews	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-conversion-and-management-x	Elsevier	3.895

Table 2. Relevant Journals & conferences for MAELSTROM's Consortium

Action Plan:

1. Each time partners identify one interesting Call for papers/articles they wish to apply to are invited to communicate to the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR).
2. Before submitting a scientific publication, partners are invited to send a draft version to the consortium members According to Art. 29 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement of the European Commission. (V2.0.1, May 2015) "Beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of - unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate."
3. Therefore, "Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests."
4. According to Art. 29 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement of the European Commission. (V2.0.1, May 2015) « Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results."
5. In coordination with the article's authors, CIMA translates the scientific publication into an informative article to be disseminated across multiple channels (website, social media, networks).

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6. All partners contribute to the promotion and dissemination of the various publications.

- **Technical brochure**

At the end of year 4 a technical brochure will be designed and produced as a project's legacy and containing main technical and technological components of the plastic remediation solutions proposed by the MAELSTROM project. The brochure will be originally in English and then translated into the partners' languages for dissemination at national level. It will be available mainly in electronic format on the MAELSTROM's website. Printed copies will be produced respecting the ecological printing standards, such as vegetable inks and certified FSC paper. A specific action plan for the technical brochure production has not yet been designed at the present date but should be set up by the end of the second year.

5.3.3. Physical interactive dissemination

Project-organized events, workshops/trainings and participation at external events and conferences will contribute to the various WPs objectives, spreading project's outputs to the respective target audiences while facilitating valuable feedback from respective stakeholders and providing ground for policy discussion and brainstorming. Depending on the global COVID-19 pandemic situation physical interactive dissemination events might need to be adapted to digital and/or hybrid formats.

In total 21 dissemination events are foreseen to take place during project's lifetime. Main events will happen in the pilot countries – Italy and Portugal, alongside Spain. Table 4 lists the main events planned to be organized during the project cycle, including dissemination conferences, beach clean-ups, info-days, demonstrative workshops, and specific capacity building actions.

Project's Events & Workshops		
	Title	Status
Kick-off meeting	MAELSTROM Kick Off Meeting	03-04-05/02/2021
Dissemination Events	Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	Done: 03/06/2020
	Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project	06/2022
	Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	06/2023
	MAELSTROM Final Workshop & Conference – Porto, Portugal	2024
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Venice, Italy on World Ocean/World Environmental Day	Done: 05/06/2021 Next: 06/2022 Next: 06/2023 Next: 06/2024
	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Porto, Portugal on World Clean Up Day	Next: 17/09/2021 Next: 09/2022 Next: 09/2023 Next: 09/2024
	Yearly clean ups (2 in total) & Info Day – San Sebastian, Spain	Next: 09/2022 Next: 06/2023
Demonstration Workshops	Yearly side events (3 in total) – Venice, at the International Venice Boat Show	Next: 06/2022 Next: 06/2023 Next: 06/2024
	Side event – Porto, at the Business2Sea	Next: 11/2023
Capacity Building Actions	Capacity Building on Communication & Stakeholder Engagement approaches. Target: MAELSTROM's partners/communication focal points	Replaced by monthly meetings
	Marine litter monitoring using the EMPOWER App – to happen during the 2022 clean-ups. Target: General public	2022
	MAELSTROM's technologies – instructions for use, managing and maintenance. Target: Operators	2023/2024

Table 3: List of project-organized events and workshops, both past and future.

Action Plan:

1. All project-organized events will be done in close collaboration with CIMA which will provide all the necessary communication support.

A capacity-building action focused on Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Approaches was expected to happen during the project kick off in February 2021. However, considering the constraints on interaction imposed by a 3-day virtual kick-off meeting and considering the need to build a common and continuous ground among communication focal points, CIMA proposed substituting the one-off capacity-building event with a monthly/bimonthly meeting (starting in February). Meetings regard project's communication and stakeholder engagement aspects and have so far revealed very useful for the internal and external communication flow. So far four Communication Meetings took place through the Teams Platform. A summary of the contents of the meeting is described on Table 5:

Communication meetings	
Meeting	Summary
Communication Meeting # 1 25.02.2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Focal points' introduction ▪ Validation of partners' description to use on social media and official communications ▪ Social Media dynamics and partner's tasks ▪ Website proposed structure ▪ News and updates from partners and general communications from the project coordinator
Communication Meeting # 2 23/03/2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MS TEAMS channel for internal communication ▪ Presentation and discussion on project flyer final approval ▪ Presentation of MAELDROPS infographics ▪ Brainstorming on of first project video contents ▪ Overview of social media behaviour
Communication Meeting # 3 04/05/2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of project graphic kit updated with new EU guidelines ▪ Overview of social media behaviour ▪ Approval of video storyboard

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Information on June's first workshop/clean up action in Venice ▪ Communication requests from partners
Communication Meeting # 4 24.06.2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recap on Maelstrom's first event. ▪ Discussion and approval of the Dissemination and Communication Plan ▪ Information on Porto's clean up event, to be held in September 2021

Table 4: Summary of Communication Meetings

Action Plan:

1. CIMA to organize the communication meetings by sending a doodle to communication focal points.
2. Communication meeting to take place on the most voted day, lasting on average 1 hour, with some pre-arranged topics, always leaving free time for partner's questions and issues.

- **Participation at external conferences and events**

Participation at several external events, technical (fairs, exhibitions) and scientific (conferences, congresses, etc.) are foreseen to scale up the dissemination impacts of MAELSTROM. This channel of dissemination will be used to facilitate knowledge sharing, personal interaction, and community building with targeted audiences. MAELSTROM's partners will use their participation in external events as an additional opportunity to establish synergies with other initiatives having similar scopes to avoid duplication of efforts, save resources and create synergies whenever possible. All partners will look for major events in the field to contribute to.

Action Plan:

1. Partners inform and provide details on their planned participation to events to CIMA and to the Project Coordinator – CNR-ISMAR.
2. CIMA provides the necessary communication/graphic support, when needed (ex. poster layout, power point presentation) and announces the project participation on project's website and social media.

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3. After each external event, partners send CIMA a short news providing information on their participation, with links and presentation materials.
4. When necessary, CIMA will further develop the contents received, directly with participants, before publishing on project's website and social media channels.

International Events & Conferences to consider participation		
TBMCE International Conference on Technologies and Business Models for Circular Economy	https://tbmce.um.si/	09/2021
Plastic Free World Conference & Expo	https://www.plasticfree-world.com/	11/2021
PowerGen Europe / Utility week	https://www.enlit-europe.com/pge	11/2021
International Society for Circular Economy (IS4CE) Conference	https://www.is4ce.org/en/	03/2022
ICPRWM 2022: 16. International Conference on Plastic Recycling and Waste Management	https://waset.org/plastic-recycling-and-waste-management-conference-in-july-2022-in-rome	06/2022
European Robotics Forum	https://erf2022.eu/	03/2022
International conference on Robotics & Automation - ICRA	https://www.ieee-ras.org/conferences-workshops/fully-sponsored/icra	2022 and/or 2023 and/or 2024
IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)	https://www.ieee-ras.org/conferences-workshops/financially-co-sponsored/iros	2022 and/or 2023 and/or 2024

Table 5: Relevant International Events and Conferences for MAELSTROM's Consortium

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External Events & Conferences attended in the first six months		
Title	Website	Date & Participants
ITEM project	https://itemworkshop.rspvify.com	13/01/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
EU Biovoices Project Conference	https://www.biovoices.eu/#	14/01/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
Blue Med Conference	Blue Med Conference	22-23-24/02/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul	https://www.bigmarker.com/inscricao/Ciclo-de-Webinares-Entrana-Onda-pelo-Ambiente-23-de-abril?show_live_page=true	23/04/2021 – CIIMAR
Chioggia Higher Education School & Fishermen Association		13/05/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/events/2021-european-maritime-day_en	21/05/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies	https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/	26/05/2021 - Deltares
EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter'	https://www.claim-h2020project.eu/claim-will-be-presented-at-the-european-research-executive-agencys-cluster-meeting/	01/06/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
Quantia Event		08/06/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
AreaAperta Primavera	https://comunicazione.cnr.it/evento/398/evento-conferenza-areaperta	16/06/2021 – CNR-ISMAR
BlueMed Hackathon 2021	https://www.cnr.it/it/news/10199/un-a-sfida-tra-idee-il-bluedmed-hackathon-ideas-and-solutions-for-a-healthy-plastic-free-mediterranean-sea	17/06/2021 - CNR-ISMAR

Table 6: Events and Conferences attended in the first six months (from January 2021 to June 2021)

5.4. Partnerships and interplays with related initiatives

Collaborations and synergies will be established with similar and complementary EU and country level projects, aimed at knowledge sharing, result's optimization, and practical applications. Partnerships with relevant public or private actors, such as waste management and recycling companies that might be interested in supporting

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the project, will also be explored through joint dissemination activities. Table 7 identifies possible partnerships and interplays with relevant initiatives taking place in the European space.

On this regard, a Memorandum of Understanding was established with Ecopolietilene (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>), an Italian consortium for the recycling of waste from polyethylene goods. Ecopolietilene is an autonomous, non-profit system recognized by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea Protection. It is made up of manufacturers, distributors, and recyclers of polyethylene goods. Ecopolietilene will provide the recycled plastic material from which to build real size whale characters to be exposed during project events.

Related projects/initiatives		
Name	Description	
InNoPlastic	EU H2020 project 2021 – 2024 Development and demonstration of plastic cleaning technologies based on a combined social and technical removal strategy methodology	https://www.innoplasic.eu/
ITEM	National funded Italian project Development of technological innovations to protect marine ecosystems	https://www.senato.it/applicazioni/xmanager/projects/leg18/attachments/documento_evento_procedura_commissione/files/000/310/401/Documentazione_Prof_Boero_-_UNIVERSITA_FEDERICO_II_e_CN-ISMAR.pdf
Biovoices	EU H2020 project Bioeconomy	https://www.biovoices.eu/
marGnet	EU project EASME/EMFF/2017 Mapping and recycling of ML and Ghost nets on the seafloor	www.margnet.eu/
Go Jelly	EU H2020 project Develop, test and promote a gelatinous solution to microplastic pollution by developing a TRL 5-6 prototype microplastics filter made of jellyfish mucus	https://gojelly.eu/
CLAIM	EU H2020 project Five innovative technologies to prevent litter from entering the sea and to monitor ML	https://www.claim-h2020project.eu/

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GHOST	LIFE+ Techniques to reduce the impact of ghost fishing gears and to improve biodiversity in North Adriatic coastal areas	http://www.life-ghost.eu/index.php/it/
ENDURUNS	EU H2020 project Development and demonstration of a sea mapping autonomous unmanned vehicle powered by hydrogen fuel cell	https://enduruns.eu/
EPHEMARE	JPI OCEANS Ecotoxicological effects of microplastics in marine ecosystems	http://www.jpi-oceans.eu/ephemare
AMARE	MED Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) through shared methodologies and geospatial tools in n Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)	https://amare.interreg-med.eu/
EVER-EST	Virtual Research Environment for Research Lifecycle management for the Earth Science community	https://ever-est.eu/
RETRACKING	INTERREG ITALY - SLOVENIA Traceability of products in Fiber Reinforced Composites (CFR)	https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/retracking
Plastic Busters MPA	MED Biodiversity natural ecosystems conservation in pelagic and coastal marine protected areas by consolidating Mediterranean efforts against marine litter	https://plasticbustersmpas.interreg-med.eu/
SEA CHANGE	EU H2020 project Change the way European citizens view their relationship with the sea	https://www.seachangeproject.eu/
UTOFIA	EU H2020 project Photochemistry at the Ocean's Surface: Effects and Interactions of Dissolved Organic Matter with Microplastics	http://www.utofia.eu
SEA LITTER CRITTERS	EU H2020 project Self-sufficient vessel able to pick up marine litter and to treat it on board for volume reduction and energy recovery.	http://www.oceansplasticcleanup.com/Cleaning_Up_Operations/Critters_Sea_Litter.htm
PLASTICIRCLE	EU H2020 project Improvement of the plastic packaging waste chain	https://plasticircle.eu/home/

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POLYCE	EU H2020 project Post-Consumer High-tech Recycled Polymers	https://www.polyce-project.eu/
Preventing Plastic Pollution	Interreg France and UK Understand and reduce the impacts of plastic pollution in the marine environment	https://preventingplasticpollution.com/
BIO Nov – PyroTech	EU H2020 project Conversion of plastic waste into biofuels	https://pyrotechenergy.com/
PlasticsFatE	EU H2020 project Fate of micro/nano plastics in marine life	https://www.plasticsfate.eu/
MIX-UP	EU H2020 project novel approach to the circularity of the plastic life cycle	https://www.mix-up.eu/project
Blue World Institute	Networking for Research, Education and Conservation	https://www.blue-world.org/
EIT Climate KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC), working to accelerate the transition to a zero-carbon, climate-resilient society	https://www.climate-kic.org/

Table 7: Possible partnerships and Interplays with related initiatives

MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic collaboration

MAELSTROM is meant to closely cooperate with its sister project In-No-Plastic, under the same call (ID: H2020-FNR-2020 - Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter). Both projects will contribute to the goal of the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development aiming at “*a clean ocean where sources of pollution are identified and removed*”.

Under this light, maximum cooperation among In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM consortiums will be pursued. This will be particularly relevant for stakeholder’s engagement, communication, and dissemination efforts. The benefits of having a common task force among the two teams are multiple:

- to create synergies among both projects towards disseminating a culture of awareness regarding marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems, within projects’ pilot geographical areas and beyond.
- to promote and give visibility to the **experimentation** of different innovative technological solutions for the removal and recycling of marine litter, within a sustainable circular economy approach.
- to promote the **transfer and adoption** of In-no-Plastic and MAELSTROM technologies by local administrators, showing its environmental and social benefits.
- to optimize resources, ideas, creativity, and efforts among both projects’ communications teams.
- to widely highlight the multiple **efforts** being made towards a common goal - *to tackle the marine litter* - with the full support of the European Union

MAELSTROM & In-No-Plastic planned joint dissemination efforts		
SEGMENT	GOAL	HOW WILL WE COLLABORATE?
RESEARCH/ACADEMIA	To catalyse and apply scientific research regarding marine litter for societal wellbeing.	Whenever suitable, MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic and will be jointly presented at scientific events such as forums, seminars, and international conferences. Joint scientific publications on the impacts of marine litter removal on coastal ecosystems will also be considered.
INDUSTRIAL	To promote effectiveness, impact and adoption of technological tools for the removal and transformation of marine litter within a circular economy paradigm.	Whenever suitable, MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic will be jointly presented in innovation and technological-related events and demonstration meetings, such as the International Business2Sea (Portugal) and the International Venice Boat Show (Italy). Moreover, the MAELSTROM App will be widely promoted by In-No-Plastics, both within its industrial consortium's partners as well as other relevant stakeholders.
DECISION/POLICY MAKERS	To promote strategies and policies to reduce the accumulation and impacts of marine litter in coastal ecosystems, through innovative removal and recycling solutions.	MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic will work together and review the expected strategic policy recommendations documents to be produced as part of projects activities.
CIVIL SOCIETY	To create a culture of awareness regarding marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems and promote a shift in consumers behaviour to decrease the consumption	MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic will jointly organize and benefit from citizen targeted communication activities such as clean-up events and info-days. Both projects will engage

	<p>and generation of new potential marine litter</p>	<p>in brainstorming on the most suitable audio-visual and face-to-face communication products and tools for awareness raising.</p> <p>Moreover, the EMPOWER App developed by In-No-Plastic will be widely promoted by MAELSTROM, both during clean ups and on its communication efforts, through the web, social media, and audio-visual materials.</p>
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Table 8: MAELSTROM & In-No-Plastic planned joint dissemination efforts

MAELSTROM and In-NO-Plastic Communication Collaboration (cont.)

MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic will collaborate to support each other in achieving wide visibility and coherent outreach. This will include highlighting the sister project logo on each project’s website, as well as in other audio-visual communication materials (leaflet, videos, infographics, etc.). Further efforts will also include joint social media campaigns and public posts/statements on marine-litter related issues.

The combination of key and strategic events will also be an asset as seen in the recent *International workshop on “Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and opportunities”*, an event designed to be part of In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM activities. The event served the purpose of scouting knowledge, initiatives and interplay opportunities for plastic removal and economic circularity in the EU space. The selection of representatives to attend the event will enrich the MAELSTROM stakeholder database, which expect to be the starting point of the “Marine litter and Plastic Strategy Working Group”, contributing towards a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions among European initiatives regarding marine litter prevention and removal actions.

Synergies alike will represent an opportunity to enhance the joint dissemination and communication efforts of both projects via the medium of Venice Lagoon Plastic Free as a joint catalyzer.

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6. Communication Strategy

6.1. Objectives and expected impacts of the communication activities

The present communication strategy refers to ongoing and future efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting MAELSTROM project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences - including the media and the public - engaging whenever possible in a two-way exchange.

In support to the described dissemination activities, broad communication actions will be undertaken aimed at promoting project's drivers, objectives, activities, and findings in a clear and intelligible way to multiple stakeholders, including civil society at large. In alignment to the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the 2030 Agenda and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSDF), MAELSTROM's communication efforts will also focus on raising awareness regarding marine litter dynamics, associated impacts and solutions. Special attention will be given to young generations, fostering a shift in plastic consumption, and associated responsible behaviours. Main communication objectives are:

- Support project's dissemination objectives and activities, through communicative materials and actions.
- Ensure maximum visibility on the project's events, key facts, objectives, and findings across identified stakeholders.
- Raise public awareness on marine litter and responsible behaviours within civil society at large.
- Promote the EU and International frameworks on Plastics and Sustainable Oceans.

6.2. Communication players and audiences

Although the communication coordinator - CIMA - will carry out the leadership of the project communication activities, all partners are expected to support and pro-actively engage. Strong linkages with the partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, leading the In-No-Plastic communication activities and with vast experience on plastic public awareness events, are already in place and expected to continue throughout the project duration. Linkages with CNR-ISMAR past and present activities in the plastics

field, alongside initiatives with artists and schools in Venice, Savona and Porto will be strongly supported by CIMA's Communication Department.

Citizens, Young Generations and Local Administrations will be targeted to raise their awareness regarding marine litter impacts, focusing on plastic consumption and preventive behaviours to avoid environmental damage and societal costs. Communication efforts will invite audiences to think about plastic production and waste, citizen responsibility and circular economy potentials. All these actions are expected to change the way audiences perceive marine litter, and how themselves can be part of a global movement, towards sustainable oceans and societies.

6.3. Communication tools and channels

Communication efforts split in two main clusters:

- **internal communication:** it regards partner's appropriate and in time exchange of information.
- **External communication:** it regards the exchange of information among the project, with stakeholders and society at large.

As such, communicative approaches need to adapt, using the most appropriate tools and channels to guarantee a good communication coverage in both clusters.

6.3.1. Internal communication

Good internal communication is a key element to allow for a collaborative environment and effective and coordinated external communication. Considering the need to build a common ground and a continuous flow of information among the Consortium members, two main actions were put in place:

- a **Microsoft Teams channel** - for real-time communication among focal points, allowing for documents sharing, online meetings and sharing of a project's calendar.
- **monthly communication meetings** for partner's focal points (started in 02/2021) – focused on project's communication and stakeholder engagement aspects. Monthly/bimonthly meetings were set to replace the Capacity Building Action foreseen during the Kickoff meeting and will last for the entire project time

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frame. Its frequency and duration will be adapted according to the communication focal point's needs.

So far four communication meetings took place through the Microsoft Teams platform. A summary of the meetings contents was described previously, in Table 5.

6.3.2. External communication

External communication initiatives are a key aspect of MAELSTROM's aim on engaging stakeholders and creating citizen awareness. As such, a significant investment was done in the first six months of the project timeframe in creating the basis of other external communication activities planned. Tables 4 and 7 indicate main external events to be considered. External communication efforts were classified in five main actions:

- Multimedia KIT (project logo, ppt/word templates, web banners, project flyer, project roll-up, videos, project website and gadgets)
- Social media channels and media coverage
- Events' media coverage guidelines, press releases and project newsletters
- Real size recycled plastic whale characters
- Events, workshops, schools', and artists' engagement

6.3.2.1. Multimedia KIT

An extensive multimedia kit was prepared aiming at creating a strong and unique visual identity. All materials are available and downloadable through MAELSTROM's website (www.maelstrom-h2020.eu) and include the following:

- Logo | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

MAELSTROM's logo was designed by a professional designer and attempts to represent both through lines, shapes, and colors the key project elements. The logo was studied to perform well in multiple settings and colors, from

traditional paper printing to T-Shirts, Web, Apps and a stamp for plastic gadgets.

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Figure 3: MAELSTROM's logo – design by CIMA

- **Power Point and Word Templates & Presentation** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

Visually coordinated Power Point and Word templates, following the EU graphic rules, were developed for internal and external presentations and report activities. Partners were invited to use those versions in all activities related to the project.

An official PowerPoint presentation was also created, highlighting the main project components and aims.

- **Website** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/>

MAELSTROM's website is presently online, and it will be maintained 5 years beyond the project's closure.

The website was developed using WordPress CMS technology and its design considers five categories:

- **Home:** Introduction to the marine litter issue, short cuts to main pages, Newsletter subscription, Latest news, Link to partner's homepages, Link to social media

- **About:** What does MAELSTROM does? Work Packages, What's in for me; Partner's description, Link to social media
- **Outputs:** Technologies; Project's Network, Link to social media
- **Media:** News archive, Events calendar, Newsletters, Media Kit, Videos, Press Reviews, Link to social media
- **Forum:** basis of the webinar events (from October 2021) feeding the Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions, Link to social media.

MAELSTROM's website will be the main source of information regarding project's activities, events, and milestones. The contents and IT maintenance and access to the website are under the responsibility of CIMA and any questions should me send to info@maelstrom-h2020.eu

Figure 4: MAELSTROM's website – Homepage

- **Web Banners and Infographics** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

A set of official infographics/images properly identified with MAELSTROM's logo was prepared to support partners on documenting and/or posting their participation in the project. Images are suitable to be used on web and social media platforms.

- **Flyer** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

The first MAELSTROM's flyer was designed and approved by communication focal points and represents MAELSTROM's cycle, relating it with the circular economy cycle. The flyer is now available in English, and it will soon be translated in partners' local languages, depending on their presence at local/national events. Few copies were printed, using vegetable inks and FSC certified paper. Illustrations and infographics were chosen, considering their role in presenting information in a visually attractive and straightforward manner.

- **Roll-Up & Flag** | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

MAELSTROM's roll up follows the same graphic approach as the flyer and other graphic materials, providing a little more detail on project's phases. Roll-ups and external flags were designed to be used in events, conferences, and clean-up initiatives.

Figure 5: MAELSTROM's flag, roll-up and flyer during the Joint MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic International Workshop, Venice, 03/06/2021

- **Video** | <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iR1nLvMRrJk>

The first project video was set up in time for the first International Workshop held in Venice on June 3rd, before the expected deadline. The video offers a good overview of the marine litter issue, an insight into the project's goals and on the two innovative technologies to be implemented in Portugal and in Italy, also calling for citizen engagement on project events.

In total 4 short videos and 1 final video regarding project's activities and technical outputs will be developed and disseminated. The production of the videos will be closely linked to the project activities, results and products of the different work packages and will be designed in tight collaboration with the Consortium members.

Figure 6: MAELSTROM's video projection during Joint MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic International Workshop, Venice, 03/06/2021

▪ Gadgets

Recycled plastic gadget are foreseen to be produced during the second year of the project, making use of the Precious Plastic (<https://preciousplastic.com/>) machinery acquired by CIMA within a local funded project. The gadget making initiative will be an opportunity to engage schools of the Savona area. Students participating in the initiative will be engaged in awareness-raising moments, beach clean ups, gadget design and gadget production. Possible gadgets include keyrings, magnets, plates, pencil cases, among others. To this regard, CIMA has started collecting and shredding plastic lids from local schools. Considering the impossibility of visiting schools in a COVID-19 pandemic context, CIMA has provided teachers with an informative pack regarding marine litter, marked with MAELSTROM's visual identity. The pack includes a cardboard collection container, informative posters, stickers and an USB with infographic videos and other interactive materials suitable to each age range and previously produced within past projects and initiatives.

Other gadgets such as natural tissue bags, glass water bottles for refilling, and cotton T-shirts will be featured and distributed to the public during the info days, clean ups, and workshops.

Figure 7: MAELSTROM's Clean-Up T-shirts, Venice, 03/06/2021

Figure 8: MAELSTROM's Clean-Up T-shirts, Venice, 03/06/2021

6.3.2.2. Social Media Channels and Media coverage

Social networks offer good opportunities of reaching multiple audiences and engaging them throughout the project. Within MAELSTROM, social media profiles were created with two main targets:

- Dissemination of Scientific and Technological Outcomes: mainly through LinkedIn and Twitter
- Citizen Awareness: mainly through Facebook and Instagram

Hashtags to accompany posts were created following EU guidelines and trending topics, according to each social media's characteristics:

**#maelstrom #marinelitter #sustainableblueeconomy #ciculareconomy
#plasticpollution #plasticfree #sdg14**

No specific study was made before creating the accounts. The aim was to make project information accessible to as many people as possible, ranging from experts to entrepreneurs, policy makers, youth, and civil society at large. To this regard, CIMA's team has created an editorial project called MAELDrops, short "pills" of information accompanied by graphic illustrations on MAELSTROM's and marine-litter related themes, posted about every three weeks. Sources of

information to feed the MAELDrops come from EU reports and accredited websites and aim at translating technical information into informative visuals to create awareness and engage citizens, while also promoting the project.

Maeldrops – every 3 weeks

Figure 9: MAELDrops

Figure 10: MAELDrops

6.3.2.3. Events' guidelines, press releases and project newsletters

- **Events' Guidelines:** information pack to support partners efforts on events' media coverage were prepared for the kickoff meeting and can be consulted in Annex 1.
- **Press releases** are prepared by CIMA before key events, in coordination with the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR) and the organizing partner(s). All press releases can be downloaded from the MAELSTROM's website. Partners are asked to translate press releases in their own language and further disseminate them to the local media channels and other relevant communication stakeholders. In this way press releases serve as a coherent and common baseline for external communication across partners and countries.
- **E-Newsletters** will be issued every six months and made available through the project web site and sent directly to the stakeholders mailing list.
- **External Media Coverage** will be encouraged by contacting directly local media officers. Press reviews will be collected, through the help of partners and by having activated Google Alert services and displayed on project's website dedicated section: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/>

6.3.2.4. Real size recycled plastic whale characters

Three real-sized plastic sperm whale installations will be created with recycled plastic provided by Ecopolietilene consortium with whom the project has established a MoU. Real-size whales will be showcased at the MAELSTROM's main public events in Porto, Venice and San Sebastian and aim to catch attention and to create awareness on the marine litter impacts for marine life.

The first whale installation is expected to be exhibit during Porto's clean-up event on September 18th, 2021, while the other two are expected to be displayed in the summer of 2022, during clean-ups events in Venice and San Sebastian. All whales will be exhibited though the entire project duration, during clean-up events and info-days. Whales' installations will be accompanied by an informative totem

regarding the MAELSTROM's description and the impacts of marine litter in marine ecosystems.

Figure 11: Recycled Plastic Whale mockup

Figure 12: Recycled Plastic Real-Size Whales - technical drawings

Figure 13: Recycled Plastic Real-Size Whales - technical drawings

6.3.2.5. Events, workshops, schools, and artists' engagement

Besides the events already reported on Table 7, MAELSTROM will be engaging with other direct forms of communication, such as school engagement and plastic artistic initiatives. Herewith a summary a brief description of main cluster events:

- **Yearly clean-up campaigns** will be organized at the two pilot locations - Venice, Porto area - along with the shore's areas of Saint Sebastian in Spain. These events aim at enhancing awareness on marine litter impacts, circular economy and sustainable development and describe MAELSTROM's project activities and expected outcomes.
- **Info-days** will be organized on occasion of clean up campaigns in the demo sites of Porto area and Venice. The first-year info-days will focus on presenting the project to participant citizens, the second year will illustrate the technologies applied in the demo sites and the third-year info-days will present main project results.
- **2 side-events** will be held one in Venice and one in Porto during the 3rd year for a joint demonstration workshop of blue technologies applied to ML removal

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and prevention. The side-event in Porto will be held within the Business2Sea, an international event, that addresses oceans' health and the sustainable use of marine resource. The Venice side-event will take place within the International Venice Boat Show, held in coincidence of the International Environment and World Ocean days in June.

- **A Final Conference** will be organized in Porto by CIIMAR. This Final Conference titled: "Removing Plastic from the seas through automated technologies" will summarize the overall achievements of MAELSTROM. The Conference Venue will be in New Cruise Terminal Building within the Porto Cruise Terminal, in the city of Matosinhos (great Porto), giving it a wide media coverage.
- **Capacity Building Actions** will target three main audiences:
 - **MAELSTROM's communication focal points** – appropriate communication and stakeholder engagement approaches- Originally planned to happen during the kickoff meeting, replaced by monthly meetings
 - **Citizens** – formative moment regarding collected marine litter and its classification for recycling (Venice, yearly), using technological Apps.
 - **Operators** – workshop on the use and maintenance of the MAELSTROM removal solutions (Venice and Porto area)

▪ **Schools & Artists Engagement**

Young generations are key for a future sustainable development. As such, the project foresees the involvement of schools in Venice (CNR-ISMAR and VLPF headquarters) and Savona areas (CIMA headquarters). Students and teachers at selected schools will be involved in clean up events, info days and gadget production while being given important information regarding the marine litter challenge. Other forms of involvement, such as contests regarding marine litter innovative solutions, will also be considered to engage young generations in addressing global and cross-cutting challenges. MAELSTROM, through CNR-ISMAR, was part of the panel of the BlueMed Hackathon 2021, a team challenge to develop ideas and solutions for a Healthy Plastic Free Mediterranean Sea, to promote sustainable blue growth and circular bioeconomy in the Mediterranean. (<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/bluedmed-hackaton/>)

Collaboration with artists using plastic waste as a main material will also be envisioned and are being currently discussed among CIMA and CNR.

Figure 14: School Kit delivering, Savona area 2021

Figure 15: Collected Plastic from schools

Figure 16: Shredded Plastic, sorted by color

ANNEX 1

SOCIAL MEDIA GUIDELINES #1

Developed for the Virtual Kick Off Meeting
03/02/2021 - 05/02/2021

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- WELCOME TO H2020 MAELSTROM

Dear communication focal point for the H2020 MAELSTROM Project, we are glad to have you making part of the MAELSTROM's team!

Our aim with this document is to provide you some guidelines to cover our first project meeting which, due to COVID-19 constrains will be held virtually. Of course, presenting each other's from a screen it will not be the same as face-to-face event but together we can overcome this challenge and, while waiting for better days, find innovative solutions to create synergies and shared visions for the future!

We kindly ask you to help us on disseminating MAELSTROM's aims, activities and milestones by engaging actively with its social media channels.

We are present in the following social networks:

Facebook: [MaelstromH2020](#)

Twitter: [@H2020MAELSTROM](#)

LinkedIn: [MAELSTROM_H2020](#)

Instagram: [maelstrom_h2020](#)

- POSTS SUGGESTIONS

We have preprepared some ready-made posts to cover the kickoff meeting in social media in case you run out of inspiration (or time). Please feel free to do you own posts anytime, just remember to add the following key hashtags:

[#marinelitter](#) [#blueeconomy](#) [#H2020](#) [#SDG14](#) [#europeangreendeal](#) [#plasticfree](#)
[#recycle](#) [#sustainability](#) [#circulareconomy](#) [#costalecosystems](#)

- to tag our funders at: [@EU_H2020](#) and [@EUScienceInnov](#)
- and to tag the project according to it social ID

(Facebook: [MaelstromH2020](#); Twitter: [@H2020MAELSTROM](#); LinkedIn: [MAELSTROM_H2020](#); Instagram: [maelstrom_h2020](#))

Facebook

- ⇒ [@MaelstromH2020](#) is kicking off! Funded by the [EU_H2020](#) and [@EUScienceInnov](#) the project will be dedicated to the mitigation of [#marinelitter](#) impacts on [#costalecosystems](#). In the next four years, an international partnership of research centres and private sector companies will study the

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distribution, the impact and the removal of marine litter through technological solutions which will lead to its recycling. The project will foster a #circulareconomy paradigm as promoted by the #europeangreendeal. Follow us online for the next updates!

- ⇒ "Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development" this is the message of #SDG14 @globalgoalsUN. This is also the goal of the @EU_H2020 @MaelstromH2020 project officially launched in these days: follow us to find out how we intend to identify, collect and recycle #marinelitter impacting #coastalecosystems. #europeangreendeal supports #circulareconomy @EUScienceInnov
- ⇒ Remove. Recycle. Give marine litter a new use. Repeat! @MaelstromH2020 project has just started! An international partnership of research centres and private sector companies is gathering for a 3-day virtual kick off meeting. Together, the team will study the distribution, the impact and the removal of #marinelitter through technological solutions which will lead to its recycling. The project will foster a #circulareconomy paradigm as promoted by the #europeangreendeal. Follow us online for the next updates!

Twitter

- ⇒ @H2020MAELSTROM project kicks off. Together with @EU_H2020 and @EUScienceInnov we will be working towards safeguarding #coastalecosystems and achieving a #sustainableblueeconomy. Stay tuned, website online soon!
- ⇒ #marinelitter Remove. Recycle. Give marine litter a new use. Repeat. @H2020MAELSTROM project starts now @EU_H2020 and @EU_H2020. The project will foster a #circulareconomy paradigm as promoted by the #europeangreendeal. Follow us online for the next updates!
- ⇒ #marinelitter Remove. Recycle. Give marine litter a new use. Repeat! This is our motto. Will it be yours too? Follow us @H2020MAELSTROM and discover our work on the preservation of #coastalecosystems towards a #circulareconomy @EU_H2020 @EU_H2020

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LinkedIn

- ⇒ Welcome MAELSTROM_H2020! A project funded under the @EU_H2020 Programme and dedicated to the reduction, removal and recycling of #marinelitter. A partnership of 14 international scientific centres and private sector companies will work together to understand how and where waste concentrates in coastal areas and which are its impact on #costalecosystems. Innovative technologies will then be employed to remove the accumulated marine litter and to prevent it from reaching the sea. MAELSTROM will also provide solutions to sort and recycle the collected marine litter and give it new strategic uses in accordance with the Circular Economy Action Plan of the European Union @EUScienceInnov. Our mantra is: Remove. Recycle. Give marine litter a new use. Repeat. Will it be yours too? #circulareconomy #europeangreendeal

Instagram

- ⇒ Welcome maelstrom_h2020! A project funded under the @EU_H2020 Programme #europeangreendeal and dedicated to the reduction, removal and recycling of #marinelitter. A partnership of 14 international scientific centres and private sector companies will work together to understand how and where waste concentrates in coastal ecosystems and which are its impacts on the #environment. Stay tuned!
- ⇒ Remove. Recycle. Give marine litter a new use. Repeat! This is our mantra. Will it be yours too? maelstrom_h2020 project has just started with a 3-day virtual kick off meeting among 14 partner institutions @EU_H2020 and @EUScienceInnov. Identify, Remove, Recycle and Marketize #marinelitter to safeguard costal ecosystems, #sea, and to promote a #circulareconomy towards the #europeangreendeal and #SDG14.
- ⇒ "Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development" this is the message of #SDG14 @globalgoalsUN and it is also the goal of the @EU_H2020 @maelstrom_h2020 project, officially launched in these days: follow us to find out how we intend to identify, collect and recycle #marinelitter impacting the #sea. The #europeangreendeal fully supports a #circulareconomy! @EUScienceInnov

- PARTNERS' SOCIAL ID's

In case you also want to tag out partners herewith their social ID's:

	Facebook	Twitter	Linkedin	Instagram
CNR	@CNRsocialFB	@CNRsocialL	@Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	@cnrsocial
Deltares	@DeltaresNL	@DeltaresNL	@Deltares	
Institute for Sustainable energy - UOM	@universityofmalta	@UMmalta	@University of Malta	@ummalta
ISDI Group				
CIMA Research Foundation	@CIMAFoundation	@CIMAFoundation	@CIMA Research Foundation	@cimafoundation
GEES Recycling srl	@fiberglassrecycling			
Venice Lagoon Plastic Free	@PlasticFreeVeniceLagoon			@plastic_free_venice_lagoon
Tecnalia	@Tecnalia	@tecnalia	@Tecnalia Research & Innovation	@tecnaliaoficial
Alpha Consult			@ALPHA Consult	
CIIMAR	@ciimar.up.pt	@CiimarUp	CIIMAR	
Servizi Tecnici Venezia				
The Great Bubble Barrier	@TheGreat Bubble Barrier	@Bubble_Barrier	@TheGreat Bubble Barrier	@thegreatbubblebarrier
MAKEEN		@MAKEEN_Energy	@MAKEEN Energy	
CNRS-LIRMM	@cnrs.fr	@CNRS		@cnrs

Please feel free to contact us on your activities and milestone anytime at the email: info@maelstrom-h2020.eu

- Other contact details

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